

FORMULATION AND OPTIMIZATION OFF HERBAL PEEL-OFF MASK

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ABSTRACT

Herbal peel-off masks, derived from plant extracts, form a thin film on the skin that is removed after drying to deliver cleansing, moisturizing, and protective effects without stripping natural oils. Rich in phytochemicals, they are particularly suitable for acne, eczema, and psoriasis, offering soothing, antioxidant, and antimicrobial benefits. In this study, formulations containing *Clitoriaternatea* and *Aloe barbadensis* were prepared and evaluated for physicochemical properties, antioxidant activity, and antimicrobial efficacy. Optimization using Design Expert Software (version 13) balanced polymers, actives, and excipients to achieve stable masks with uniform film formation and enhanced bioactivity. Antioxidant potential was confirmed by DPPH assay, with formulation F8 showing the strongest activity and significant differences (**p < 0.001 vs. control). Antimicrobial testing revealed inhibition zones up to 19 mm. Overall, F8 emerged as the optimized peel-off mask, combining stability with superior antioxidant and antibacterial properties.

Keywords: *Clitoriaternatea*, *Aloe barbadensis*, DPPH assay, Design Expert Software(DOE), Optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal peel-off masks form a thin film on the skin, removed after drying to provide immediate cleansing and rejuvenation. Unlike rinse-off masks, they adhere to the skin, eliminating impurities, dead cells, and excess oil while preserving the moisture barrier. Phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenolics, and polysaccharides impart antioxidant, antimicrobial, and soothing effects, making them suitable for sensitive and acne-prone skin. *Clitoriaternatea* (butterfly pea flower) contributes anthocyanins and flavonoids with strong antioxidant activity, while *Aloe barbadensis* (aloe vera) offers moisturizing, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial benefits. Their combination provides synergistic potential for skin health. Optimization using Design Expert Software (version 13) balanced key parameters-viscosity, drying time, peel strength, and spreadability to ensure uniform film formation, hydration, and stability. This study integrates traditional herbal knowledge with modern cosmetic science to establish a validated peel-off mask formulation that delivers therapeutic benefits and meets consumer expectations.

LIST OF MATERIALS

Table No:1: List of materials used for the preparation of the formulation

Sl. No	List of materials	Role
1	Clitoriaternatea flower extract	Antioxidant
2	Aloe Vera extract	Antimicrobial
3	HPMC K 15	Gelling agent
4	Polyvinyl alcohol	Film forming agent
5	Sodium benzoate	Preservative
6	Glycerin	Moisturizer
7	Distilled water	Vehicle

EXTRACTION OF CLITORIA TERNATEA POWDER

Fresh clitoriaternata flower was collected, dried and crushed. The powder weighed, soaked in distilled water for 15-30 minutes, and heated at 60-70 °C for 30-45 minutes with occasional stirring. The mixture

was cooled, filtered through muslin cloth, and left overnight. The clear blue filtrate was collected.

Fig No:1:Extract Of Clitoriaternatea

EXTRACTION OF ALOE VERA GEL

Fresh aloe vera leaves were washed, drained vertically for 10–15 minutes to remove latex, and trimmed to discard spiny edges and rind. The inner gel was scooped, homogenized, filtered through muslin

cloth, and stored in an airtight container.

Fig No:2:Aloe Vera Gel

FORMULATION TABLE

Table No:2:Formulation chart of herbal peel off mask

Ingredient	Clitoriaternatea powder extract	Aloe vera gel	HPMC K15	Sodium benzoate	PVA	Glycerine	Distilled water
F1	4.7ml	3.5g	0.26g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F2	4.3ml	3.8g	0.36g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F3	4.0ml	4.0g	0.46g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F4	3.6ml	4.3g	0.56g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F5	4.3ml	3.5g	0.66g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F6	5.0ml	3.4g	0.2g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F7	3.2ml	4.4g	0.86g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F8	3.9ml	3.8g	0.76g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F9	3.0ml	4.9g	0.56g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F10	4.5ml	3.7g	0.26g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F11	4.80ml	3.4g	0.26g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F12	3.5g	4.5g	0.46g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F13	4.0ml	3.8g	0.66g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F14	2.50ml	5.2g	0.76g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F15	5.00ml	2.5g	0.96g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml

F16	3.20ml	4.2g	1.06g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml
F17	4.40ml	3.5g	0.56g	0.04g	0.5g	1.0ml	10ml

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Optimization is the processing of adjusting variables to achieve the most desirable outcome. In cosmetics, it ensures that a product is not only effective but also safe, stable, and pleasant to use.

BOX-BEHNKEN

Box-Behnken Design is statistical tool under Response Surface Methodology (RSM). It is widely used in pharmaceutical and cosmetic research for optimization because it requires fewer experiments compared to full factorial designs. BBD generates combinations of factor levels.

Table No:3: Observed Values Of Responses

		Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Response 1	Response 2	Response3
Std	Run	Polymer Concentration	Mixing Time	Herbal Extract Concentration	Drying Time	Peel Off Time	Antioxidant Activity
		%w/w	min	%w/w	min	Sec	%
5	1	0.1	15	1	24	50	48
4	2	0.5	20	3	22	56	42
10	3	0.3	20	1	23	53	43
15	4	0.3	15	3	16	48	60
16	5	0.3	15	3	16	46	62
6	6	0.5	15	1	19	58	64
12	7	0.3	20	5	16	50	55
17	8	0.3	15	3	15	52	75
11	9	0.3	10	5	15	30	63
14	10	0.3	15	3	18	52	61
9	11	0.3	10	1	20	52	50
13	12	0.3	15	3	17	53	59
8	13	0.5	15	5	16	45	72
3	14	0.1	20	3	24	55	47
1	15	0.1	10	3	17	54	49
7	16	0.1	15	5	21	55	53
2	17	0.5	10	3	19	50	71

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Table No:4 Phytochemical screening

SL.NO	Phyto constituents	Observation	Inference	Picture
1	Anthocyanins	Formation of green with a fading colour	Presence of anthocyanins	
2	Flavonoids	Formation of yellow coloured precipitate	Presence of flavonoids	
3	Tannins	A black colour is formed.	Presence of tannins.	
4	Alkaloids	An orange colour is formed.	Presence of alkaloids.	

5	Saponins	Persistent foam formation	Presence of saponin	
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

ANOVA FOR QUADRATIC MODEL- DRYING TIME

Response 1: Drying Time

Table No:5: ANOVA Of Drying Time

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	128.83	9	14.31	3.75	0.0475	significant
A-Polymer Con	12.5	1	12.5	3.28	0.1132	
B-Mixing time	24.5	1	24.5	6.42	0.039	
C-Herbal extract con	40.5	1	40.5	10.62	0.0139	
AB	4	1	4	1.05	0.3399	
AC	0	1	0	0	1	
BC	1	1	1	0.2622	0.6244	
A ²	33.01	1	33.01	8.65	0.0217	
B ²	7.12	1	7.12	1.87	0.2142	
C ²	2.69	1	2.69	0.7065	0.4284	
Residual	26.7	7	3.81			
Lack of Fit	21.5	3	7.17	5.51	0.0663	not significant
Pure Error	5.2	4	1.3			
Cor Total	155.53	16				

Std. Dev.	1.95	R²	0.9200
Mean	18.71	Adjusted R²	0.8800
C.V. %	10.44	Predicted R²	0.8000
		Adeq Precision	12.5000

Table No:6: Fit Statistics Of Drying Time

Table No:7: Fit Summary Of Drying Time

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0258	0.0469	0.3825	0.1469	Suggested
2FI	0.8746	0.0276	0.2487	-0.5932	
Quadratic	0.0581	0.0663	0.8800	0.8000	Suggested
Cubic	0.0663		0.8663		Aliased

Table No:8 :Lack Of Fit

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0258	0.0469	0.3825	0.1469	Suggested
2FI	0.8746	0.0276	0.2487	-0.5932	
Quadratic	0.0581	0.0663	0.6076	-1.264	Suggested
Cubic	0.0663		0.8663		Aliased

Response 2:Peel Off Time

Table No:9: ANOVA For Peel Off Time

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	538.69	9	59.85	4.3	0.0339	Significant
Fig No:3: Contour Of Drying Time						
B-Mixing time	98	1	98	7.03	0.0329	
C-Herbal extract con	136.12	1	136.12	9.77	0.0167	
AB	6.25	1	6.25	0.4485	0.5245	
AC	81	1	81	5.81	0.0467	
BC	90.25	1	90.25	6.48	0.0384	
A ²	91.04	1	91.04	6.53	0.0378	
B ²	5.09	1	5.09	0.3656	0.5645	
C ²	34.2	1	34.2	2.45	0.1612	
Residual	97.55	7	13.94			
Lack of Fit	60.75	3	20.25	2.2	0.2305	not significant
Pure Error	36.8	4	9.2			
Cor Total	636.24	16				

Std. Dev.	3.73	R²	0.9000
Mean	50.53	Adjusted R²	0.8725
C.V. %	7.39	Predicted R²	0.7810
		Adeq Precision	10.8462

Table No:10: Fit Statistics Of Peel Off Time

Table No:11: Lack Of Fit Of Peel Off Time

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Linear	362.19	9	40.24	4.37	0.0845	
2FI	184.69	6	30.78	3.35	0.1312	
Quadratic	60.75	3	20.25	2.2	0.2305	Suggested
Cubic	0	0				Aliased
Pure Error	36.8	4	9.2			

Table No:12:Fit Summary Of Peel Off Time

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit pvalue	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0986	0.0845	0.2282	0.2561	
2FI	0.1044	0.1312	0.443	0.5533	
Quadratic	0.1069	0.2305	0.8725	0.7810	Suggested
Cubic	0.2305		0.7686		Aliased

Fig No:5: Contour Of Peel Off Time

Fig No:6: 3D Surface Of Peel Off Tim

Response 3: Antioxidant Activity

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	1353.83	9	150.43	3.99	0.0407	significant
A-Polymer Con	338	1	338	8.97	0.0201	
B-Mixing time	264.5	1	264.5	7.02	0.033	
C-Herbal extract con	180.5	1	180.5	4.79	0.0648	
AB	182.25	1	182.25	4.84	0.0638	
AC	2.25	1	2.25	0.0597	0.8139	
BC	0.25	1	0.25	0.0066	0.9374	
A ²	22.76	1	22.76	0.6042	0.4624	
B ²	327.92	1	327.92	8.7	0.0214	
C ²	14.02	1	14.02	0.3723	0.5611	
Residual	263.7	7	37.67			
Lack of Fit	90.5	3	30.17	0.6967	0.6009	not significant
Pure Error	173.2	4	43.3			
Cor Total	1617.53	16				

Table No:13: ANOVA For Antioxidant Activity

Table No:14:Fit Statistics Of Antioxidant Activity

Std. Dev.	6.14	R ²	0.9200
Mean	57.29	Adjusted R ²	0.8915
C.V. %	10.71	Predicted R ²	0.7684
		Adeq Precision	11.8000

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Linear	661.33	9	73.48	1.7	0.3211	Suggested
2FI	476.58	6	79.43	1.83	0.2899	
Quadratic	90.5	3	30.17	0.6967	0.6009	Suggested
Cubic	0	0				Aliased
Pure Error	173.2	4	43.3			

Table No:15:Lack Of Fit Of Antioxidant Activity

Table No:16:Fit Summary Of Antioxidant Activity

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	AdjustedR ²	PredictedR ²	
Linear	0.0306	0.3211	0.365	0.1344	Suggested
2FI	0.454	0.2899	0.3573	-0.1727	
Quadratic	0.0819	0.6009	0.8915	0.7684	Suggested
Cubic	0.6009		0.5717		Aliased

Fig No:5: Contour Of Antioxidant Activity

Fig No:6: 3D Surface Of Antioxidant Activity

ORGANOLEPTIC EVALUATION

Table No:17: Organoleptic evaluation

SL.NO	PARAMETERS	OPTIMIZED FORMULATION
1	State	Semi-solid
2	Colour	Blue
3	Odour	Aromatic
4	Texture	Smooth
5	Consistency	Good

Fig No:7: Formulations Of Herbal Peel Off Mask

Parameters	Optimized formulation(F8)	Mean±SD
pH	Good	5.28±0.02
Viscosity	Good	6009±0.82(cps)
Drying Time	Good	20±1.0
Homogeneity	Good	Good
Spreadability	Good	5.26±0.20

Table No:18: Evaluation Parameters Data

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Antimicrobial activity was evaluated using *S.aureus* against tetracycline as control.

Table No:19:Antimicrobial Activity

SL.NO	FORMULATION	ZONE OF INHIBITION(mm)
1	Sample	19.0
2	Control	24.0

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

The radical scavenging activity of different samples were determined by using DPPH assay according to *chang et al(2001)*.The decrease in the absorption of the DPPH solution after the addition of an antioxidant was measured at 517nm. 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl is a stable free radical with pink colour which turns yellow when scavenged. The DPPH assay uses this character to show free radical scavenging activity. Antioxidants react with DPPH and reduce it to DPPH-H and as consequence the absorbance decreases. The degree of discoloration indicates the scavenging potential of the antioxidant compounds or extracts in terms of hydrogen donating ability. All the analysis was performed in triplicates and average values was calculated. The best set of values is showed below:

Fig No:8: Antimicrobial Activity

Concentrations(μ L)	Absorbance	Percentage of Inhibition(%)
Control	0.8000	0.0000

Standard- Ascorbic acid		
1.25	0.3610	54.8750
2.5	0.2750	65.6250
5	0.216	73.0000
10	0.1200	85.0000
20	0.0710	91.1250
Sample code-Sample		
1.25	0.7440	7.0000
2.5	0.6800	10.5000
5	0.6000	26.0000
10	0.5040	37.3750
20	0.4000	47.6250

Table No:20: Antioxidant Values

Fig No:9: DPPH Assay

Fig No:10: Graph of Sample

Fig No:11:Graph of Standard

CONCLUSION

The herbal peel-off mask containing *Clitoria ternatea* peel extract and aloe vera was successfully formulated. The extract of *Clitoria ternatea* peel was prepared and incorporated with suitable excipients to obtain peel-off mask formulations of varying concentrations. The optimized formula F8 were evaluated using various parameters. Antibacterial activity was assessed by the agar plate diffusion method through the determination of the zone of inhibition. The results demonstrated that the herbal peel-off mask exhibited significant antibacterial properties. Furthermore, antioxidant activity was evaluated using DPPH assay, and the findings of the present investigation indicate that the herbal peel-off mask containing *Clitoria ternatea* peel extract possesses good antioxidant potential. pH, viscosity, spreadability, drying time and homogeneity of F8 formulations was evaluated.

Based on the findings of the present study, the formulated herbal peel-off mask demonstrated effective activity against various skin infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*. As the formulation was developed using natural ingredients with a minimal amount of chemical excipients, it is considered safe for topical application.

Furthermore, the formulation of the herbal peel-off mask exhibited notable antioxidant activity. Among them, formulation F8 was identified as the optimized formulation due to its superior performance. The major advantage of the optimized peel-off mask is its ability to rejuvenate and hydrate the skin, thereby improving overall skin texture.

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